

STUDIES IN SESQUITERPENES. PART XV. SYNTHESIS OF
4-*iso*PROPYL-6-METHOXYTETRALONE-1

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The preparation of 4-*iso*propyl-6-methoxytetralone-1, a potential intermediate in the synthesis of cadinene, is reported.

For the synthesis of cadinene, 4-*iso*propyl-6-methoxytetralone-1 (I) appears to be an attractive intermediate; its preparation has been described in the present communication.

The starting material for the synthesis of (I) was 7-methoxytetralone-1 (XIII), which was, in turn, obtained by the ring-closure of γ -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-butyric acid (XII). Useful modifications (vide Experimental) were effected in its preparation, resulting in much economy in time. The intramolecular acylation of the acid (XII) was most conveniently carried out by the application of polyphosphoric acid (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 257).

The next step was the preparation of the tetralin (XIX) from the tetralone (XIII); the straightforward synthesis involving its reaction with *iso*propylmagnesium halide could not be accomplished as the reaction always gave a mixture consisting of the unchanged tetralone, its reduction product the tetralol (II), and high boiling condensation products. The absence of the Grignard-addition product was established by a study of the dehydration of the crude reaction product; the elimination reaction was not quite facile and the product consisted almost entirely of the dialin (III); this hydrocarbon was identified by its hydrogenation to the tetralin (IV) which on chromic acid oxidation (Burnop *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 730; Stork, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 576; Thomas and Nathan, *ibid.*, 1948, 70, 331) furnished the crystalline ketone (V). This condensation could not be effected by the use of either *iso*propylmagnesium iodide (Shine, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 8) or *iso*propyllithium (Young and Roberts, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1444).

The reaction of *isopropylmagnesium bromide* with 2:4:7-trimethyltetralone-1 (VI) (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1948, 28, 69) or 2:4:5:7-tetramethyltetralone-1 (VII) (Gupta and Muthana, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1953, 35, 310) has been reported to proceed in a normal fashion. In the present case, it is rather difficult to see, why this anomalous reaction takes precedence. A study of the space model (Catalin Molecular Models) of 7-methoxytetralone-1 (XIII) showed the absence of any steric hindrance at the carbonyl function. The induction effect (-I) of the methoxy group is not expected to be appreciable at the site of the keto group.

A number of similar cases have been recorded in the literature. Thus, 5:8-dimethyltetralone-1 (Cocker *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2355), 4:7-dimethylindanone-1 (Herz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 73), 6-methylindanone-1 (Wagner-Jauregg, Arnold and Huter, *Ber.*, 1942, 75B, 1293) and 4:6-dimethylindanone-1 (Wagner-Jauregg and Hippchen, *Ber.*, 1943, 76B, 694) have all been shown to undergo the abnormal reaction with *isopropylmagnesium halide*.

Since this route to 1-*isopropyl-7-methoxytetralin* (XIX) failed, an alternative synthesis, as outlined below, was developed.

255m μ and 280 m μ . Whereas the latter band is to be ascribed to the anisol system (Dorfman, *loc. cit.*), the absorption at 255m μ is rather unexpected and it is likely that the material may be contaminated with the corresponding isopropylidene isomer, which is expected to absorb (cf. Juday, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3008) strongly at about 10 m μ towards the shorter wave-lengths as compared to the chromophore in (XVa). The olefin on hydrogenation over Pd-CaCO₃ catalyst furnished the desired 1-isopropyl-7-methoxytetralin (XIX). This synthesis enabled us to prepare (XIX) in an overall yield of 62% based on the tetralone (XIII).

In view of the known chromic acid oxidation (Burnop *et al.*, *loc. cit.*; Stork, *loc. cit.*; Thomas and Nathan, *loc. cit.*) of 6-methoxytetralin (IV) to the tetralone (V), and a number of other similar recorded instances (McNiven, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 1725; Buchi and Pappas, *ibid.*, 1954, 76, 2963; Ritchie *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, 76, 723) of oxidation, it was anticipated that 4-isopropyl-6-methoxytetralone-1 (I) could be easily obtained from the tetralin (XIX) by such an oxidation. This was readily realised and the ketone could be prepared in a yield of 70-75%. The yield of the tetralone could be raised to 85% by the use of sodium dichromate-acetic acid mixture (Corey and Ursprung, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 183; Fieser, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 4386). Oxidation of the tetralin (XIX) by hydrogen peroxide in presence of vanadium pentoxide (Treibs *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1953, 86, 616) afforded the ketone in 19% yield only. The structure (I) for this ketone is supported by the light absorption data (Fig. 1). As expected, the position of the maximum is identical with that of 6-methoxytetralone-1 (V).

*(Contd.) For thermal fission, the following transition state appears attractive :

In the case of a cleavage in acid media, the reaction can be rationalised as under :

FIG. 1

Work on the conversion of 4-isopropyl-6-methoxytetralone-1 into cadinene is being pursued.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction with the boiling range 40°-60°. The solvent extracts were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The spectra were taken on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

β-(*p*-Anisoyl)-propionic Acid.—The following procedure was found to be more convenient (cf. Fieser and Hershberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 2315; Dauben and Adams, *ibid.*, 1948, 70, 1759).

Anisol (108 g., 1 *M*), succinic anhydride (110 g., 1.1 *M*) and dry nitrobenzene (500 c.c.) were placed in a 3-litre 3-necked flask, carrying a slip-sealed stirrer and a calcium chloride guard-tube. The mixture was chilled in ice-salt and with stirring was introduced anhydrous aluminium chloride (293 g., 2.2 *M*) in four lots during 1½ hours. The reaction mixture was stirred at the ice-bath temperature for 3 hours and then replenished the ice-bath and left aside overnight (12 hours). Next day it was

again stirred at room temperature (25°) for 6 hours and the rose-coloured reaction mixture was poured on ice (1.5 kg.) and HCl (400 c.c.). Due to sparing solubility in nitrobenzene, most of the acid separated out and was filtered off and washed with benzene-ether mixture (1:1; 100 c.c. × 4). From the filtrate, the solvent layer was separated and the aqueous portion extracted with ether (100 c.c. × 3). The combined solvent extracts were washed with water (200 c.c. × 1) and the keto-acid was extracted out with aqueous sodium hydroxide (10% ; 50 c.c. × 3). Acidification of the alkaline solution gave some more (15-20 g.) acid. The combined crude keto-acid was thoroughly washed with water and dissolved in ammonium hydroxide (15%), the solution was boiled for 2 hours (with occasional addition of water to prevent undue concentration) to drive off traces of nitrobenzene and after clarification with active carbon, was acidified to furnish the desired product as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 144-47° (Fieser and Hershberg, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 147-48°), yield 190 g. (91%). The material was used as such for the next step.

γ-(*p*-Anisyl)-butyric Acid (XII).—The Clemmensen reduction of the above keto-acid was effected in the following much less time-consuming manner (cf. Martin, "Organic Reactions", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1942, Vol. I, p. 167).

Zinc wool (175 g.) was amalgamated with mercuric chloride (17.5 g.), HCl (20 c.c.) and water (175 c.c.) by shaking for 10 minutes and decanting off the aqueous solution. To this the above keto-acid (140 g.) and HCl (conc., 1200 c.c.) were added. While the mixture was gently refluxed for 5 hours, HCl (conc., 280 c.c.) was introduced portion-wise each hour. The hot reaction mixture was filtered off through a plug of glasswool; the unchanged zinc was washed with boiling water (100 c.c. × 4). From the filtrates the reduced acid that had crystallised out was collected. The zinc wool was washed with warm sodium bicarbonate solution (10% ; 100 c.c. × 2) and acidification of the alkaline washings yielded a further quantity of the desired acid. The combined *γ*-(*p*-anisyl)-butyric acid was powdered and well washed with water and dried. This was distilled to yield the pure acid, b.p. 161-63°/1 mm, m.p. 61-62°, in 120 g. (92%) (Martin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1438, reports m.p. 61-62°).

γ-Methoxytetraione-1 (XIII).*—Polyphosphoric acid (PPA), prepared from P₂O₅ (270 g.) and syrupy phosphoric acid (*d* 1.75, 116 c.c.) in an 1-litre 3-necked flask fitted with a Hershberg stirrer, was maintained at a temperature of 80° for 1 hour and the molten *γ*-(*p*-anisyl)-butyric acid (90 g., 0.49 *M*) was added in one lot. This was thoroughly stirred at this temperature for 5 minutes and the homogeneous reaction mixture was left aside at 80° for another 25 minutes *without* stirring. The reddish brown product, while still hot, was at once poured on crushed ice containing some ether (100 c.c.). For the sake of convenience, the material was left aside overnight to decompose the complex. The product was taken up in ether (80 c.c. × 4), washed with water (25 c.c. × 2), aqueous NaOH (5% ; 25 c.c. × 2) and brine (20 c.c. × 3). The neutral solution was dried, the solvent distilled off (column) and the residue purified by distillation, b.p. 130-32°/0.5 mm, m.p. 66-67°, yield 72 g. (88%) (*lit.*, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 66-67°). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 253 m μ (ϵ , 9580).

*For references see "Encyclopaedia of Organic Chemistry", Elsevier Publishing House, Amsterdam, 1940, 12 B, p. 2666.

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (H_2SO_4 method) was obtained as glistening deep orange-red rods from pyridine, m.p. 278° (decomp.). (Found: N, 15.64. $C_{17}H_{16}O_5N_4$ requires N, 15.73%).

Action of isoPropylmagnesium Bromide on (XIII).—In a typical experiment, a solution of 7-methoxytetralone-I (8.8 g., 0.05 M) in ether (50 c.c.) was gradually introduced with continuous swirling to a well-cooled (ice-bath) solution of isopropylmagnesium bromide (from Mg 1.55 g., 0.064 g. atom, isopropyl bromide 8 g., 0.065 M and ether 80 c.c.). As each drop of the ketone solution came in contact with the Grignard solution, a red colour developed, which vanished immediately on swirling. From the clear pale green solution no solid complex separated (even after standing). The reaction mixture was left overnight (12 hours) and then refluxed for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The cooled reaction mixture was decomposed by pouring on ice and H_2SO_4 (10 c.c.). The ether layer was separated and the aqueous portion extracted with ether (20 c.c. $\times$ 3). The extracts were washed with water and dried. Removal of the solvent furnished a viscous liquid residue (9.0 g.).

This material (0.28 g.) on treatment with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine reagent yielded the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of 7-methoxytetralone (0.18 g.), m.p. $275-77^\circ$, undepressed by an authentic sample. This showed that the material contained about 34% of 7-methoxytetralone.

Another portion (8.0 g.) was added slowly (1 hour) to freshly flushed sodium hydrogensulphate (0.5 g.) contained in a 10 c.c. modified Claisen flask, maintained at $160-70^\circ$ and arranged for vacuum distillation. The distillate (3.8 g.) came over at $97-113^\circ/1$ mm and a polymeric residue was left. The volatile material was fractionated to furnish two fractions: (i) b.p. $94-97^\circ/2$ mm, 1.0 g. and (ii) b.p. $106-120^\circ/2$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.5585, 2.7 g. The first fraction was redistilled over sodium to afford a mobile liquid, b.p. $93-95^\circ/1$ mm, η_D^{30} 1.5745, yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 82.19; H, 7.96. $C_{11}H_{12}O$ requires C, 82.5; H, 7.5%). That this material was essentially 7-methoxy-3:4-dihydronaphthalene (III) was established by catalytic hydrogenation over palladium on calcium carbonate to 7-methoxytetralin (IV) (b.p. $109-11^\circ/4$ mm, η_D^{30} 1.5405, yield 70%), which was in turn oxidised by chromic acid in acetic acid to 6-methoxytetralone (V), m.p. $78-79^\circ$ (benzene-petroleum ether); mixed m.p. with an authentic sample was not depressed. The second fraction, which failed to solidify, but gave a positive test with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine and reacted with sodium, was presumably a mixture of the tetralone (XIII) and the tetralol (II).

Ethyl 1-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-1- α -propionate (XIV).—The procedure was patterned after that of Bachmann and Wendler (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2582).

Freshly cut, clean zinc-wool (25.5 g., 0.39 g. atom) was covered with thiophene-free benzene (200 c.c.) and the 7-methoxytetralone (56.0 g., 0.35 M) was added. The mixture was refluxed and some solvent (about 50 c.c.) was tapped off to remove the last traces of the moisture from the system. This was cooled, and dry ether (100 c.c.) together with $1/5$ th of ethyl α -bromopropionate (75.6 g., 0.39 M ; 54 c.c.) was intro-

duced. The reaction was initiated by warming and adding a crystal of iodine. After the reaction had started, the balance of the bromo-ester was let in during 1½ hours. The reaction mixture was gently refluxed till all the zinc had disappeared (6 to 15 hours). After heating for another 2 hours, the product was cooled (0°) and glacial acetic acid (35 c.c.) and water (175 c.c.) were added cautiously. The solvent layer was separated and washed with dilute acetic acid (10%, 90 c.c.), followed by washing with brine containing ammonium hydroxide. Removal of the solvent yielded the crude hydroxy-ester (91.8 g.) as a viscous liquid. An attempt to fractionate the crude ester under reduced pressure at 2 mm ended up in an almost quantitative recovery of the starting 7-methoxytetralone-1 (*vide supra*). It was hence directly dehydrated as follows.

Ethyl 7-Methoxy-3:4-dihydronaphthalene-1-2-propionate (XVa).—A mixture of the above crude hydroxy-ester (91.8 g.) and formic acid (90%, 184 c.c.) was heated by immersing in a boiling water-bath for 1 hour. The product was cooled, diluted with water (500 c.c.) and extracted with petroleum ether (80 c.c. × 3). The combined extracts were washed with water (25 c.c. × 2), aqueous sodium bicarbonate (10% ; 30 c.c. × 3), finally with brine (20 c.c. × 2) and dried. This was stripped off the solvent and the residue fractionated (Vigreux column, 10") to afford the unsaturated ester (XVa) as a somewhat viscous liquid with a faint yellow tinge, b.p. 164-66°/2 mm, η_D^{25} 1.5435, yield 75 g. (93%) (Paranjape *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report b.p. 175°/25 mm).

An analytical sample (central cut) had b.p. 152°/1 mm, η_D^{25} 1.5435, d_4^{25} 1.090, M_b 75.28 (calc. 73.11, $E\Sigma_D$ 0.84); $\lambda_{\max}^{EtOH}$ 220 m μ (ϵ , 21380), 261m μ (ϵ , 6030) and 305 m μ (ϵ , 2960). (Found: C, 73.89; H, 7.94. $C_{16}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 73.85; H, 7.69%).

Saponification of the ester (2 g.) by refluxing with NaOH (1.6 g.) in water (5 c.c.) and ethanol (8 c.c.) for 3 hours afforded the corresponding acid (XVb), m.p. 110-12°, in a quantitative yield. Two crystallisations from dilute acetic acid furnished long, white rods, m.p. 117° (Paranjape *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, described as a liquid, b.p. 215°/25 mm). (Found: C, 72.18; H, 6.84. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 72.41; H, 6.90%).

Ethyl 7-Methoxytetralin-1-2-propionate (XVIa).—The above unsaturated ester (XVa: 42 g.) in ethanol (50 c.c.) was shaken with pre-reduced Pd-CaCO₃ (Busch *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1916, 49, 1063; 1929, 62, 1458) (5 g.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen at laboratory temperature and pressure. The reduction came to a close after 2 hours when 101% of the theoretical quantity of hydrogen had been absorbed. The catalyst was removed by filtration and washed with ether (50 c.c.). The solvent was removed from the filtrate through a column under slight suction. Fractionation of the residue furnished the required product (XVIa) as a colorless, viscous liquid, b.p. 160-62°/2 mm, η_D^{27} 1.5245, yield 41.4 g. (98%).

An analytical sample had η_D^{20} 1.5210, d_4^{20} 1.067, M_b 74.74 (calc. 73.58, EM_D 1.16, $E\Sigma_D$ 0.44). (Found: C, 73.26; H, 8.45. $C_{16}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 73.28; H, 8.40%).

A sample (0.5 g.) of this ester was hydrolysed as above to furnish the saturated acid (XVIB), m.p. 70-76°, yield 0.2 g. After three crystallisations from benzene-petroleum ether, it was obtained as stout, white prisms, m.p. 85°. (Found: C, 72.25; H, 7.94. $C_{14}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 71.79; H, 7.69%).

An attempt to prepare the saturated acid directly from the unsaturated ester (XVa) by the Raney-nickel alloy-alkali method (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 513) resulted only in the isolation of the unsaturated acid (XVb).

β-1-(7-Methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthyl)-*n*-propanol (XVII): (i) *By Lithium Aluminium Hydride Reduction*.—The above saturated ester (XVIa: 5.24 g., 0.02*M*) in ether (25 c.c.) was reduced with a slurry of LiAlH₄ (0.95 g., 0.025 *M*) in ether (25 c.c.) in the usual manner, and worked up with 10% H₂SO₄ (70 c.c.) at below 0°. The alcohol (XVII) was isolated as a colorless, thick liquid, b.p. 150-52°/0.8 mm, η_D^{26} 1.5510, d_4^{20} 1.081, M_D 64.89 (calc. 64.21), yield 3.94 g. (90%). (Found: C, 76.25; H, 9.0. C₁₄H₂₀O₂ requires C, 76.36; H, 9.09%).

(ii) *By Bouveault-Blanc Reduction*.—Bright sodium (37 g., 1.62 g. atom; 50% excess) was placed in a dry 3-necked flask, fitted with a Hershberg slipseal stirrer, a condenser, a dropping funnel and connected to a system for maintaining nitrogen atmosphere. The sodium was immediately covered with anhydrous toluene (75 c.c.) and heated in an oil-bath at 120° and stirred to disperse the sodium. A mixture of the saturated ester (XVIa: 72 g., 0.27 *M*), anhydrous *tert*-butanol (72 g., 1.0 *M*) and toluene (100 c.c.) was added during 1 hour with stirring under nitrogen atmosphere. The bath temperature was maintained at 120° ± 5° throughout the addition. The stirring and heating were continued for a further period of 30 minutes. The product was cooled, finally in an ice-bath and cautiously treated with small lots of ice-water with swirling. After 250 c.c. of water had thus been introduced, the toluene layer was separated and washed with water (50 c.c. × 4). The alkaline washings and the previous aqueous portion were mixed and extracted with ether (75 c.c. × 3). The combined solvent extracts were washed with dilute acetic acid (5% ; 100 c.c. × 1) and finally with brine (75 c.c. × 2). After drying, the solvents were fractionated off and the residue distilled (column): b. p. 152°/0.8 mm, $\eta_D^{26.5}$ 1.5510, yield 55 g. (93%). In this preparation the inert atmosphere is necessary to avoid the discoloration of the reaction mixture towards the end, with the consequent loss in the yield.

2-(7-Methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthyl-1)-propene (XVIII).—A mixture of the above alcohol (55 g., 0.25 *M*), boric acid (15.5 g., 0.25 *M*) and toluene (150 c.c.) was gently refluxed, in an apparatus suitable for the continuous removal of water, till no more water (9 c.c.) had separated (3 hours). The heating was continued for another 15 minutes during which period some toluene (20 c.c.) was tapped off. The apparatus was disconnected and the toluene was distilled off under reduced pressure (water pump). The residue was pyrolysed at an inside temperature of 330° at 1.5 mm pressure; under these conditions the distillation of the pyrolysate was quite smooth. The distillate (b.p. 116°-140°/1.5 mm) together with the condenser-washings was taken up in petroleum ether and dried over activated silica gel (10 g.). The solvent was removed and the residue fractionated over sodium (5 g.). The desired product was obtained as a colorless, fairly mobile liquid, b.p. 130-34°/4mm, η_D^{24} 1.5475, yield 38.6 g. (76.4%).

An analytical sample had b.p. 130°/4mm, η_D^{20} 1.5455, d_4^{20} 1.006, M_D 63.48 (calc. 62.23); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 255 m μ (ϵ , 2250) and 280 m μ (ϵ , 2730). (Found: C, 83.3; H, 8.71. C₁₄H₁₈O requires C, 83.3; H, 8.91%).

1-isopropyl-7-methoxytetralin (XIX).—The above unsaturated material (XVIII: 38.6 g.) in ethanol (40 c.c.) was shaken with pre-reduced Pd-CaCO₃ (Busch, *loc. cit.*) (3.8 g.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen at ordinary temperature and pressure, when the theoretical amount of hydrogen was absorbed in 8 to 9 hours. The rate of hydrogenation, which was very fast in the first hour, slowed down considerably towards the end. On working up as described under (XVIa) and fractionation over sodium, the required tetralin was obtained as a colorless, mobile liquid, b.p. 118-20°/1.5 mm, η_D^{20} 1.5365; yield 37.3 g. (96%).

A refractionated specimen (central cut) had b.p. 103-104°/0.5 mm, η_D^{20} 1.5340, d_4^{20} 1.007, M_n 63.25 (calc. 62.64, $E\Sigma_D$ 0.28). (Found: C, 82.54; H, 9.81. C₁₄H₂₀O requires C, 82.35; H, 9.80%).

4-isopropyl-6-methoxytetralone-1 (I): (i) *Oxidation by Chromic Anhydride-acetic Acid Mixture*.—*1-isopropyl-7-methoxytetralin* (13.06 g., 0.064 M) in glacial acetic acid (128 c.c.) was placed in a 500 c.c. 3-necked flask fitted with a dropping funnel and a Hershberg stirrer. This was cooled to about 8-10° and chromic anhydride (A.R., 19.2 g., 0.192 M), dissolved in water (24 c.c.) and diluted with acetic acid (54 c.c.), was slowly let in with stirring; after addition of the first few c.c., the temperature was rapidly brought down to 0° and the addition continued at that temperature. After the addition (30 minutes) the dark red reaction mixture was allowed to stand at 0° overnight (12-15 hours). This was diluted with water (500 c.c.) and extracted with ether (60 c.c. × 5). The combined ether extracts were washed with brine (15 c.c. × 3) and the solvent (ether and acetic acid) was removed under reduced pressure (water pump) from a water-bath. To the residue some benzene (20 c.c.) was added, which was distilled off to remove traces of moisture. Fractionation of the resulting product furnished the ketone as a pale yellow, somewhat viscous liquid, b.p. 145-50°/0.7 mm, η_D^{20} 1.5630, yield 10.45 g. (75%).

(ii) *Oxidation by Sodium Dichromate-acetic acid-benzene Mixture*.—A mixture of *1-isopropyl-7-methoxytetralin* (20.4 g., 0.1 M) and crystalline sodium dichromate (60 g., 0.2 M) in glacial acetic acid (300 c.c.) and thiophene-free dry benzene (150 c.c.) was stirred at 25° for 22 hours. Ethanol (25 c.c.) was added towards the end and the stirring continued for 15 minutes more. The reddish green reaction mixture was diluted with water (850 c.c.) and extracted with benzene-ether mixture (1:1, 100 c.c. × 5) and worked up as above to yield the tetralone as a pale yellow, viscous liquid: b.p. 145-47°/0.7 mm, η_D^{27} 1.5620, yield 17.5-18.5 g. (80-85%).

The tetralone, as obtained by method (i) or (ii), could not be rendered colorless by refractionation. However, the yellow impurity due to the presence of a volatile chromium complex could be best eliminated by filtering the tetralone (one part in one part of dry benzene) through two parts by weight of activated alumina (basic/I, 15 × 4 cm) followed by elution with benzene, when the impurity was strongly adsorbed at the top of the column as a green band. Removal of the solvent from the effluent and fractionation of the residue furnished a colorless liquid, b.p. 140-42°/0.6 mm, η_D^{20} 1.5630, d_4^{20} 1.093, M_n 64.04 (calc. 62.70, EM_n 1.31, $E\Sigma_D$ 0.61); λ_{max}^{EtOH} 276 m μ (ϵ , 15500). (Found: C, 77.21; H, 8.15. C₁₄H₁₈O₂ requires C, 77.06; H, 8.26%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, prepared by the sulphuric acid method, was obtained in a quantitative yield. On two crystallisations from glacial acetic acid it separated as dark red small plates, m.p. 202-202.5°. (Found: N, 13.56. $C_{26}H_{22}O_2N_4$ requires N, 14.07%).

The semicarbazone (pyridine method) after two crystallisations from dilute ethanol came out as a white crystalline powder, m.p. 163°. (Found: N, 15.27. $C_{15}H_{21}O_2N_3$ requires N, 15.61 %).

(iii) Oxidation by Hydrogen Peroxide.—1-isoPropyl-7-methoxytetralin (2.04 g., 0.01 M) in acetone (20 c.c.) was treated with hydrogen peroxide (20-25%, 6.8 c.c., 0.04 M) in presence of vanadium pentoxide catalyst (prepared from V_2O_5 , 10 mg., H_2O_2 , 20-25%, 0.1 c.c. and acetone 2 c.c.) under stirring at laboratory temperature (25°) for 24 hours. The reaction mixture was finally refluxed for 1 hour, when the colour changed from brownish red to reddish green. The solvent was distilled off and the aqueous phase together with the heavy liquid at bottom after cooling was extracted with ether-benzene mixture (1:1; 20 c.c. $\times$ 4). Removal of the solvents from the combined extracts and fractionation of the residue gave a low boiling fore-run (b.p. 108-110°/0.4 mm, η_{10}^{27} 1.5430, 0.8 g.) apparently consisting mostly of the unoxidised material and a second fraction (b.p. 128-30°/0.4 mm., η_{10}^{27} 1.5550, 0.4 g., 19%) of the required tetralone (impure), as identified by its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

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